

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See informed consent sheet

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of the anonymized transcript of the recording	[yes]
Archiving of the anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	14/07/2021
Name of the interviewer	MÓNICA DOMÍNGUEZ MARTÍN
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	JUAN MARQUINA FUENTES
Affiliation of the expert	Deputation of province of Orense
Position/Job description	General Secretary
Gender	MALE
Years of experience	20 years
Area of expertise	civil servant, legal expert
Rural and/or urban focus	RURAL/URBAN

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Part A: Introduction and General Questions

INTERPLAY BETWEEN URBAN AND RURAL MUNICIPAL GOVERNMENTS

1	In your opinion, what is the impact that increasing population movements from the countryside to cities have on local governments?
	<p>The municipalities head of the region or of the judicial party (10,000-15,000 inhabitants) maintain the population or increase a little. Above all, due to the arrival of immigrants with Galician roots and especially from Venezuela or the Demonic Republic.</p> <p>Likewise, the cities, the Galician capitals, maintain their population.</p> <p>Municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants lose population.</p>
1.1	<p><i>Do you know any public policies or best practices regarding the changing urban-rural relationships? Please consider practices in the following five areas:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Local responsibilities and public services.</i> - <i>Local financial arrangements.</i> - <i>Structure of local government.</i> - <i>Intergovernmental relations of local governments.</i> - <i>People's participation in local decision-making.</i>
	Next answer
2	To retain and, where appropriate, attract population to rural municipalities, is it more important to invest in infrastructure or to improve (or at least maintain) the provision of public services?
	Through promotion instruments or policies. The Provincial Council of Orense has a Project (with European funds), which is called "Emprende OU". Municipalities in a situation of

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	<p>population loss are defined (with less than 5,000 inhabitants or up to 10,000 inhabitants with population loss). Economic aid is provided: business / activity entrepreneurship, agricultural, livestock, new technologies ... Currently, about 100 municipalities enjoy these aid.</p> <p>There are also plans or measures to promote the birth rate, rehabilitation of homes ... within the lines of aid established in the municipalities.</p>
3.	<p>To retain and, where appropriate, attract population to rural municipalities, is it more important to invest in infrastructure or to improve (or at least maintain) the provision of public services?</p>
	<p>At the moment, the improvement of the provision of services is more important than investment in infrastructures. Especially, measures or aids for family conciliation (very important for the young population), culture, sports, social services.</p>

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

GENERAL QUESTIONS ABOUT THE PROVINCES IN TERMS OF THE PROVISION OF SERVICES

4.	<p>Indicate some factors of success/ failure of the role of the provinces in the Spanish local structure.</p>
	<p>Success: help to municipalities (more in times of pandemic), especially since the approval of Law 27/2013, of December 27, on the rationalization and sustainability of the Local Administration.</p> <p>Failure: the biggest problem is the democratic deficit, the system of election of the members of the Provincial Council. The role of the Provincial Councils should be strengthened and their democratic legitimacy improved. In practice, citizens do not know, do not identify, which people make up the provincial government. The electoral body should be better defined.</p>
5.	<p>To what extent does the province increase or decrease the centralization of power?</p>
	<p>It does not affect the decentralization of power. The provincial, in accordance with its constitutional configuration, responds to the fulfillment of the functions of the State, the peripheral State Administration and, in part, also of the Autonomous Communities.</p>

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6.	Do the provinces compete (or even threaten) the legitimacy or autonomy of the municipalities? 6. Do the provinces compete (or even threaten) the legitimacy or autonomy of the municipalities?
	Not currently, because practically all the services assumed by the municipalities need their authorization. Relations between the municipality and the province are affected by the different "political color" of the respective governments.
7.	What impact the provinces have on the execution of powers by municipalities, especially those with a population of fewer than 20,000 inhabitants (rural areas)?
	See next answers.

PROVINCIAL SERVICES

8	Does the Provincial Government provide any service in the municipality? Which one?
	Yes, a lot. Garbage collection and waste treatment (about 50 municipalities in the provinces), provincial network for the collection of animals, social services, development aid (directly by the provincial ... regime of "on-demand services").
9	<i>If the previous answer is affirmative, how do you assess the importance of this service for the municipality?</i>
	Very good perception by the municipalities because it means saving the costs of services.
10	Do you think that the City Council could manage these services if it had better financing?
	Is possible. Still, not everyone could. There is a shortage of qualified personnel (there are no personnel with adequate technical training).

TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE

11	Does your City Council receive technical assistance from the Provincial Government? And from the Autonomous Community?
	Yes, technical assistance from the provincial. Not from the Autonomous Community.
12	Does the Provincial Government collaborate in municipal procedures?
	Yes, for example, in tax collection. Most of them are thin. Also in the hiring or expropriation files: the municipalities delegate it to the provincial one. There is the Office of Assistance to Municipalities, to request reports in administrative procedures.
13	<i>Do you consider that such assistance is adequate?</i>

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	Yes, although it can be improved. There is a deficit of qualified nationals (Secretary, Secretary-controller). There are problems to fill these places.
14	<i>What is the procedure through which the City Council requests and obtains this assistance?</i>
	It is varied: punctual technical assistance: resolution of the Mayor's Office requesting help); management commission (agreement of the municipal plenary session); framework agreements (the City Council adheres) ...

DEMOGRAPHY AND POPULATION MOVEMENTS

15	Do you consider that the role of the province in the provision of services influences the migratory flow to large cities? 15.1 In what way? 15.2 Could you offer an example?
	The province tries to curb the flow of population to the cities. The capital (Orense) has about 110,000 inhabitants. The rest of the municipalities are, the majority (75) of less than 5,000 inhabitants. Only 10-12 municipalities have more than 5,000 inhabitants. How do you do / try? Through the improvement and increase of public services.
16	Does the aging of the population affect the provision of services and the role that carries the province? 16.1 To what extent?
	Yes, it affects. In particular, some social services have had to be promoted: home help, accessibility ... And this to the detriment of other services or benefits, such as family conciliation.
17	What other demographic changes affect service delivery?
	The arrival of immigrants. They are mostly Spanish speakers, so language is not a problem. But they have had to articulate aid for integration. Social services play a fundamental role.
18	In your opinion, does the municipality have a dispersed population?
	Yes. There are numerous villages (60-70) population centers with about 200-300 inhabitants.
19	If so, to what extent does dispersion affect services provision and the role of the province?
	It makes the provision of services more expensive. The supply networks for basic services (water, electricity ...) must also be maintained and it is very expensive. The aging of the population and its geographic dispersion make it necessary to rethink investments.

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20	To attract or retain the population to rural municipalities, what structure of municipal services do you consider would be more favorable?
	The role of the provincial council should be strengthened or else the merger of municipalities (or their association) should be chosen for the provision of services. It must be taken into account that the small municipalities are decreasing, they are shrinking.
21	Do you consider that the role of the province in the provision of services influences the migratory flow to larger cities? 21.1 How or in which way? 21.2 Could you offer an example?
	See the others answers.

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